

THE STYLE AND THE LANGUAGE OF BYRON'S POETRY

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Abstract. *The study of Byron's language not only makes it possible to better appreciate his poems, it also helps to study the style of the English language, and, at the same time, allows one to judge the stylistic problems that faced English writers at the beginning of the 19th century. This article discusses the use of poetic tropes in Byron's literary works thus analyzing the style and language of his poetry.*

Keywords: *personifications, metaphors, figurative language, interpretation, comparisons, generalizing and accusatory power, mythological name.*

Poetic tropes are the eternal companions of artistic thought. Their character, however, changes not only from epoch to epoch, but also from one creative individuality to another. To single out typical features in the figurative language of an individual writer does not mean to classify his tropes into types and subtypes. This would only deprive the author of his originality and obscure his true achievements in the field of literary speech. First of all, it is necessary to be aware of what goals they serve in his work, from what sphere he mainly draws them, and, finally, what interpretation he gives to those figurative means that he inherited from his predecessors. No writer is free from the influence of tradition. However, only epigones without individuality and talent mindlessly repeat what has already been said and endlessly vary their models without introducing anything essentially fresh into them. In a concrete analysis, the question of tradition usually comes first, since only by comparing the old with the new, inherited and freshly created, it is possible to decide what the stylistic innovation and stylistic skill of the poet consisted of. At the same time, it usually turns out that some tropes are either presented richer or at least better and more fully reflected the author's approach to expressive means. Thus, in Byron's works, especially in the first two periods of his work, written in London and Switzerland, personifications, metaphors and comparisons are particularly vivid. These tropes are, in general, among the most important in figurative language. Personification, in particular, received a special development in the language of the poets of the English classical school of the 18th century. The classics used it for purposes of generalization, and also - and this was perhaps less important for them - in order

to give sublimity to the poetic style, freeing it from words with a narrow meaning, that is, in the understanding of the classics, prosaic, 'low ' and 'rude'.

Byron is especially willing to use personifications in cases where it is important for him to achieve greater generalizing and accusatory power. In *The English Bards*, for example, he denounces the vice that victoriously rules English society, and calls for scourging him in satires, since those who are not shy before the law is afraid of laughter.

When Vice triumphant holds her sov'reign sway,
Obey'd by all who nought beside obey;
When Folly, frequent harbinger of crime,
Bedecks her cap with bells of every Clime;
When knaves and fools combined o'er all prevail,
And weigh their Justice in a Golden Scale;
E'en then the boldest start from public sneers,
Afraid of Shame, unknown to other fears,
More darkly sin, by Satire kept in awe,
And shrink from Ridicule, though not from Law.

(E. B., 27-36) .

and further:

Are there no sins for Satire's Bard to greet?
Stalks not gigantic Vice in every street?
Shall Peers or Princes tread pollution's path, -
And 'scape alike the Laws and Muse's wrath?

(E. B., 823-826).

In these verse of personification and metaphors serve, first of all, for generalization and reinforcements: "Vice triumphant holds her sov'reign sway", "Stalks not gigantic Vice in every street?" For distracted metaphor "pollution's path"(Byron chooses one of the strongest possible synonyms - pollution ("infect, decay"). Simultaneously he uses word with escalated importance, t.e. the word, expressing sharp, resolute actions and sharp feeling: wrath, purge, scourge, sneer, shrink and so on. As a result these lines, in significant measure built on personification, gain the nature of angry flash of indignations and differ with emotion.

Quite often Byron puts in personification mythological name contents, which by the power and width of its public and political importance far exceeds the possibility of the classicists of the XVIII century. So, in "Curse of Minerva" Athens Palladium speaks of rebellion, which threatens the Englishmen in enslaved India:

Lo! there Rebellion rears her ghastly head,
And glares the Nemesis of native dead; (C. M., 223-224).
In the same monologue, turning to England, Athens speaks:
Look last at home - ye love not to look there
On the grim smile of comfortless despair:
Your city saddens: loud though Revel howls,
Here Famine faints, and yonder Rapine prowls (239-242)
Thereby, personification gains certain fresh sense already in the first satire.

Figurativeness of the language was one of the discriminating feature of the romantic poetry. Discussing the style of Shelly, for instance, critics often name it metaphoric and note spreading of developed personification in his verse. This allows even to speak of "mythological creature" at analysis of such poems, as The Cloud, That a Skylarc or Ode to the West Wind. In these verses personified phenomenas of the nature turned into poetic allegories, cognate on its bright and many-sided figurativeness with antique myth. Byron was more moderate than Shelly. However metaphor and comparisons occupy the more significant place in his style, beginning from the first song of "Child Harold's pilgrimage". The Nature for Byron and for many of his contemporaries was an inexhaustible source of the comparisons and metaphors. In "Child Harold's pilgrimage" and other verses many of these images are used with their own accustomed association: sea is changeable, eagle or falcon is proud and do not stand the captivities, mountains are majestic and so on. So, insecurity in toughness of the success Byron illustrates with the comparison of the earth being agitated by sea, on which sails the rickety canoe:

The Earth to them was as a rolling bark
Which bore them to Eternity ... (Ch. H., IV, 64)
Freedom loving Child Harold he compares to wild bird in compels:
But in Man's dwellings he became a thing
Restless and worn, and stern and wearisome,
Drooped as a wild-born falcon with dipt wing
To whom the boundless air alone were home ... (Ch. H., Ill, 15)

The Banner of the Liberty flaps as awesome storm, streaming onward even against winds:

Yet, Freedom! yet thy banner, torn, but flying,
Streams like the thunder-storm against the wind
(Ch. H., IV, 98)

The phenomena of the nature in these metaphor and comparisons are often animated, approaching to personification, as in the last example. In stanza 89 of the third cantos of "Child Harold's pilgrimage" the sky and the land keeps quiet like that, as we keep silence, sunk in deep thought, which cannot be explained by the word:

All Heaven and Earth are still-though not in sleep,
But breathless, as we grow when feeling most;
And silent, as we stand in thoughts too deep: -
All Heaven and Earth are still:

In its turn, the wit of the person likens to the abyss, in which boils "whirling gulf of phantasy and flame":

... I have thought
Too long and darkly, till my brain became,
In its own eddy boiling and o'erwrought,
A whirling gulf of phantasy and flame: (Ch. H., III, 7)

The Feeling of the young generation is perished in the sands of the deserts and die amongst dark, rotting darnel:

... our young affections run to waste,
Or water but the desert! whence arise
But weeds of dark luxuriance, tares of haste,
Rank at the core, though tempting to the eyes,
Flowers whose wild odours breathe but agonies,
And trees whose gums are poison; (Ch. H., IV, 120).

Harmful and mad passions of the young years lead away like waterspout, absorbing in itself the power of many winds:

youth's frenzy
still it draws us on,
Reaping the whirlwind from the oft-sown winds
(Ch. H., IV, 123)

The Suffering starts the deep root in devastated heart, the nobler the ground, the better it capable to bear their corroding influence, but also that not for long:

Existence may be borne, and the deep root
Of life and sufferance make its firm abode
In bare and desolated bosoms: (Ch. H., IV, 21)

Forming in allegorical pictures, these metaphors and comparisons do not distract attention from internal symbolic sense due to image, which combine distracted with subject-concrete: tares of haste (mistakes, letters, darnels to haste),

breathe but agonies, deep root of life and so on. In these word-combination of the word, marking distracted notions (haste, agonies, life) and word, marking subject-concrete presentations (tares, breathe, root) are bound with each other much closely, for instance, by means of preposition or as verb with complement.

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